

APPROACH ON THE LONG TERM IMPACT OF THE COBOTS IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of the research presented in this paper is to identify some aspects of the acceptance dimension for Cobots used in nursing area.

Methodology/approach - Through a survey within two EU member countries, we compare the attitude of German and Romanian participants in using and accepting Cobots in nursing areas.

Findings – The results of the survey show that most participants are in general open to this technology.

Research limitations/implications – It was not possible to allow participants to have direct contact with Cobots before the survey began. Therefore, at the beginning of the survey, Cobots and Nursing Bots have been described as accurately as possible.

Practical implications – The aim of this research is to identify and represent the degree of appreciation and use of the Cobots, focused on the clinical (medical and nursing) applications. Especially, since the pandemic situation has exposed one weakness of healthcare systems, i.e. the shortage of personnel.

Originality/value – The results confirm, that the user is in general ready and that the Cobot market is set to grow from a global valuation of 475 million USD in 2020 to 600 million USD in 2021 and to a substantially 8 billion USD in 2030, considering a projected CAGR of 32.5%. (Allied Business Intelligence - ABI Research, 2021)

Key words: Cobots, Nursing, Survey

INTRODUCTION

Cobots are the synergic result of different trends that after a long period of developments achieved the necessary technological level to be promoted on the global market, including the smart sustainable manufacturing.

The industrial revolution I4.0 arrived with large political pressure on the manufacturing digitalization. Technologically the I4.0 is accompanied by new challenges in developing new sensor families and sensoria facilities, high-speed communication systems, larger access to databases and iCloud together with new managerial technologies. In this context the manufacturing robotisation started in 1960 may be applied in a totally different manner, and in totally different other domains of activities, rising organisational challenges due to the economy globalisation, population ageing, a higher demand of skilled professionals in the middle of the personnel crises in heavy work, medical and social assistance.

On this background it appears that the possibility of using Cyber-physical approaches and the Cobots as skilled, demanded and tireless workers are finding themselves in a market that needs them.

In this paper, as part of a larger research including also PhD work, the focus is on the Cobots usage within the clinical environment, considering a parallel survey within two EU member countries, Germany and Romania, and some other countries collateral data.

What is mainly compared is the attitude of German and Romanian population participants in using and accepting the application of the Cobots in clinical areas, especially for nursing activities.

The current pandemic situation – together with many kind of economic, politic and social pressure determined by the demographic evolution, the skilled workers ageing and even extinction and the changes imposed by the large and forced migration - has exposed the healthcare systems within the EU countries, one weakness of the system more than other, i.e. the shortage of personnel.

One major aim of the larger developed research is to extend the findings to a PEST analysis and help Cobots manufacturers, distributors and integrators to improve their technological and economical capacities by a better market understanding, and by becoming more profitable and with a better awareness of potential risks. It is considered that this approach will contribute to the promotion of the evolution and implementation of the Cobots by also increasing the capacity to generate long term scenarios for the Cobots lifecycle, in accordance with a specific market, forecasting their impact within a generally considered unpredictable market due to the no history and the unicity of the applications.

Within the research was considered the perspectives - opportunities and risks - from two representative countries to assure a broader perception regarding the PEST factors. One is in the middle of EU, with a technological leading economy, pretty aging population and face millions of input migrants; the other one at the far east end of EU, anon Schengen country, with an emerging market economy, strongly related (as follower) of the German economy, moderate aging population, facing with little input migrants but millions of output migrants from the active population.

As is described, based on the depicted profile of the two EU countries, it is expect to encounter different attitudes and expectations from the two type of participants having also the scaling factor in the dimension of the two populations as 4.5:1 in favour of Germany. Considering also the strong profile of the two countries, the very occidental one and a former east country, we may consider them that are bracketing EU in assumption that the findings may be extended to further markets, different digital devices and enhanced Cobots manufacturing, as long as the results are of outmost importance for the Cobots manufacturers in order to adapt their products and technologies for the client satisfaction and the market absorption capacity.

PANDEMIC CLINICAL APPROACH

In the pandemic situation, one of the main challenges was to be able to treat the critical patients in the Critical Care Units (CCU), Intensive Care Units (ICU) and Intensive Treatment Units (ITU). The necessity to protect the already insufficient, exhausted and very exposed medical personnel rose the idea to introduce robotic systems as handing help. The classical problem of the robotic systems is that they must be isolated from the human subjects and take all the necessary security measures if any human is identified entering in the robotic operational space. In the clinical environment, the robotic system must interfere with patients and medical personnel and therefore the idea to adapt Cobots used in the industrial environment to clinical applications sounds very logical.

The major handicap or impairment that promotes humans instead of robots is the manual dexterity, the incredible ability of humans to use hands in a very accurate coordinate and skilful capacity to grasp, handle and manipulate objects in large and small movements.

Therefore one of the first integrators concern was to select the available robotic system that enables an adequate locomotion and positioning (mobility), ensure a slower but quick enough arm motion with collision control with no harmful or dangerous acts (soft touch), creating in the end the required gripping system. As the integrators final target the envisaged grippers must first be able to grip and handle a variety of object sizes with an adjusted gripping force enabling the handling of delicate, brittle or heavy objects, and if necessary to possess customized “fingers”.

Working in direct connection with the medical doctors and applying the exploratory research methodology from the engineering and management point of view the experts opinion was valorised in the elaboration of an internal list that describes the identified 12 clinical staff necessities in operating robotic systems (Table 1) and 14 technical characteristics list that enables the comparison between different robotic models and the compatibility with the medical staff desires. The lists may be enriched once gathered more experience.

Table 1. Clinical staff demands

Device	Software	Operation
Simple installation	Simple programing	Integrated control board
Plug and Play on the clinical IT platform	Adjustable gripping force	Ergonomic actuation
Flexible and wide work range	Enhanced position, speed and force feedback	Mechanical keys to double the touch screen ones
Tool output extension	Upgrade on request	File safe operation

Evaluation of the survey

In this article, we want to examine the social dimension from PEST readiness of potential patients to the use nursing bots in hospitals. The comparison between Romania and Germany should provide additional information about possible reasons for a positive or negative acceptance of Cobots. The survey was conducted between August 8th 2021 and September 11th 2021 using the platform surveymonkey.com. The authors asked for participation in their social networks. Emphasis was placed on the shortest possible completion time; in fact, this averaged 3:16 minutes. The dropout rate was 0%. 61.65% of the participants were men and 38.35% women. When asked about their income, compared to the average income of each respondent country, 47.32% of the participants stated to be below average, 17.56% have an average income, 25.37% have an above average income and 9.76% did not desire to specify. An important observation is that already more than 1/3, 35.92% of the participants, had their first experience with robots. The majority (57.28%) had not yet gained any experience with robots, but seems that are aware about the topic.

General result

"Nursing robots? Such nonsense"

This quote is from Ricardo Lange, an intensive care nurse. In an interview with Katrin Göring-Eckert, a member of the Bundestag, he stated, that he can't imagine how Nursing Bots can help in the ICU. She opposed, that Nursing Bots are something to think about. Where they can be used and where not. However, she also thinks, that Nursing Bots are a bit of a pipe dream. ("Wertschätzungsmäßig Ist Das Unterste Schublade")

Lange is an advocate for caregivers in Germany. He knows the daily routine in hospitals and cannot see any great benefit in Cobots. Göring-Eckert, on the other hand, as a professional politician, recognizes Germany's current and future situation, with too few nursing staff, and thinks about possible solutions.

However, how do potential patients see it? To investigate the possible acceptance among potential patients, we hypothesize the following: Patients are generally ready for the use of Nursing Bots.

The answers of the Romanian and German participants differ with regard to the basic attitude towards Nursing Bots. Overall, 93% of the Romanian participants and 77% of the German participants consider the use of Nursing Bots to be useful in principle. In the assessment of the benefits of Nursing Bots (1 would be not useful but dangerous and 10 would be very useful), the average values are 8.05 for Romanian participants and 6.55 for German participants. It can therefore be stated that, in accordance with the authors' expectations, Romanian participants are generally more open to Nursing Bots. The final question as to whether a human specialist is preferred over Nursing Bots also confirms this picture. Here the rate was 53% for Romanian participants compared to 68%.

Usefulness in general

We asked on a scale of 1-10, how useful in general the survey participants would rate the use of Nursing Bots in everyday hospital life. The average grading of 7.09 shows that the overall acceptance is high.

Preference in general

Nevertheless, when asked to prefer a human caregiver/caretaker or a Nursing Bot, 63.11% stated, that they would prefer the nurse. 24.76% was not sure and only 12.14% chose the option Nursing Bot. Even if Cobots are seen as useful, a human nurse is preferred if to choose between both.

Non-body touching services

- For 93.63% it would be ok if a Nursing Bot cleans their room in the hospital.
- 81.37% would be ok with a Nursing Bot removing the dishes in their room after dinner.
- 73.53% would accept a Nursing Bot serve the meals into their room.
- 63.73% stated that it would be ok for them to encounter a Nursing bots on every hospital corridor.

It can be stated that non-body touching services by Nursing Bots are accepted in general.

Body-related services

When it comes to body-related services, 96.94% would accept a Nursing Bot assisting a human nurse. In turn, 23.47% would be ok with if the Nursing Bot is not assisting a human or is not being assisted by a human nurse.

When they could choose between the Nursing Staff and the Nursing Bot, the participants answered as followed:

- When performing the daily hygiene, 57.43% prefer a human nurse.
- When being fed, 52.97% again were in favour of a human nurse.
- When being moistened or creamed over the entire body, again 52.97% chose the human nurse.
- 51.98% would prefer a Nursing Bot when it comes to preparation and administration of their medication plan, but in 4 cases the percentage is pretty close to 50%.
- When injecting medication, i.e. insulin, 68.81% prefer a human.
- Interestingly, compared to an injection, when setting an infusion, the percentage that prefers a human nurse, drops to 64.85%.

General readiness

It can be concluded, that in general the participants are ready for Nursing Bots in action. However, when it comes to body-related services, the openness towards Nursing Bots is shrinking.

Attitude of German and Romanian participants

When looking at Hofstede Insights, the dimension Uncertainty Avoidance in Romania is quite high with 90. That would mean that Romanians are not open for new technology. Germany's value is at 65, which would mean that Germans are more open in comparison to new technology and therefore more open towards Nursing Bots in action. (Hofstede Insights, 2021)

Contradictory to Hofstede's Insights, the author's expectations are a bit different. Especially, due to the fact that the author's social network in Romania is focused on the area around Cluj-Napoca, which is a technologically very advanced and flourishing region.

To find out if there is a difference in preferences between the two EU members, the following hypothesize is to be validated or falsified. German and Romanian participants have a very similar attitude towards Nursing Bots.

Usefulness in general in comparison

The survey participants were asked, "On a scale of 1-10, how useful do you rate the use of nursing bots in everyday hospital life?". 1 would be not useful but dangerous and 10 would be very useful.

Romanians estimated the possible usefulness higher. Especially Romanian females would find Nursing Bots very useful. In comparison, German females rated the usefulness with only 6.23.

Table 2. German and Romanian opinion on usefulness

	Germany		Romania	
Usefulness	6.74		8.02	
	male	female	male	female
Usefulness	6.95	6.32	7.96	8.07

Attitude of participants

The hypothesis, that German and Romanian patients have a very similar attitude towards Nursing Bots has been falsified among our participants. The impact of living in an area that has a big proportion of young people together with the tech companies operating in the same region around Cluj-Napoca might have a bigger impact on openness towards new technologies.

Further data examination

In addition, we examined the data according to further criteria. The following tables provide a corresponding overview.

Age, gender and preference

We asked the participants if they could imagine seeing Nursing Bots in action in hospitals and if they would prefer human personnel to a Nursing Bot.

It can be said that men in Romania as well as in Germany can imagine the use of Nursing Bots regardless of their age. In fact, however, this percentage is higher among Romanian women than among German men. When it comes to the question of whether human professionals are preferred, it is generally true that this increases with age. Only Romanian men are an exception.

Table 3. Correlation between age, gender and preference

Country	Gender	Nursing Bots in action	Human preferred	Age	Nursing Bots in action	Human preferred
Romania	male	96%	56%	16-30	100%	64%
				30+	93%	50%
	female	90%	50%	16-30	91%	45%
				30+	88%	63%
Germany	male	80%	66%	16-30	79%	66%
				30+	85%	67%
	female	69%	71%	16-30	66%	66%
				30+	75%	81%

Income

When asked whether income has an impact (a personal assessment relative to the average income in the respective country was asked), no clear tendency can be identified. This might be explained by the fact that we assume many well-educated students among the low income participants.

Table 4. Correlation between income, gender and preference

Country	Gender	Nursing Bots in action	Human preferred	Income	Nursing Bots in action	Human preferred
Romania	male	96%	56%	low	100%	33%
				average	83%	67%
				high	100%	75%
	female	90%	50%	low	90%	60%
				average	100%	33%
				high	67%	67%
Germany	male	80%	66%	low	81%	56%
				average	70%	80%
				high	82%	74%
	female	68%	73%	low	76%	65%
				average	71%	86%
				high	80%	40%

Level of experience

The assumption that existing experience with robots could lead to greater openness towards nursing bots cannot be substantiated by the present survey either. For example, the picture among German women is exactly the opposite and experience tends to lead to a stronger preference for human professionals. But may explain higher values at the Romanian population due to direct experience and mass media advertising of the robotic application in the Covid hospitals for critical and common spaces sterilization, as imported robots ("The European Commission is donating disinfection robots to a number of hospitals in Romania - HotNews.Ro"; "EC representation in Romania"; Vasilache) and the one manufactured in Romania (MUV Smart), but also as medical assistant, the Grace robot made in Hong Kong. (Grace nurse)

Table 5. Correlation experience and preference

Country	Gender	Experience	Nursing Bots in action	Human preferred
Romania	male	yes	91%	55%
		no	100%	62%
	female	yes	100%	50%
		no	83%	61%
Germany	male	yes	80%	59%
		no	80%	75%
	female	yes	62%	85%
		no	71%	64%

Services

When asked about the use of Cobots, the respondents usually have very different possible uses in mind, which can lead to fundamental rejection or acceptance. The survey therefore asked specifically about individual services, distinguishing between services that are close to the body and those that are not.

In contrary to expectations, the acceptance of services that are not close to the body is not fundamentally higher than that of services that are close to the body. Also, the previously gained picture of a higher acceptance of Nursing Bots among Romanian participants can no longer be clearly verified.

In the case of **non-body-related services**, acceptance is highest for cleaning activities. However, around 20% of the respondents cannot imagine that robots are being used to bring food.

Table 6. Acceptance of Nursing Bots in non-body-related services

Country	Gender	Cleaning sickrooms	Cleaning dishes	Serving meals	Encounter in the corridor
Romania	male	96%	84%	84%	64%
	female	97%	67%	70%	40%
	total	96%	75%	76%	51%
Germany	male	94%	78%	74%	72%
	female	87%	91%	62%	60%
	total	92%	82%	70%	68%

In the case of closer **body-related services**, the big difference between assisted and unassisted services is immediately noticeable. Just under one fifth of the respondents can imagine being treated close to the body without additional supervision by a human. In contrast, the acceptance of a joint activity of human and COBOT is very high and is over 90% in both countries. Only 4% of German females would feel comfortable when a Cobot alone would nurse them.

Table 7. Acceptance of Nursing Bots in body-related services

Country	Gender	Total	Assisting	Unassisted
Romania	male	25	92%	40%
	female	30	93%	17%
	total	55	93%	27%
Germany	male	97	96%	28%
	female	45	82%	4%
	total	142	92%	20%

The next question was about a **basic preference between human and Nursing Bot**. It was asked in which situations the respondents would prefer a human. First of all, it is noticeable that the values are generally above 50%, i.e. the use of humans is generally preferred. However, the values are in a range that was rather surprisingly low for the authors. Interesting are the differences between the Romanian and German participants with regard to body care and body creaming. Here it seems to be clearly more important for the German participants to have themselves looked after by a person (61% and 58% respectively), while these values are only 40% each for the Romanian participants. Interestingly, the Romanian participants' values are higher than those of the German participants only for the preparation of the medication plan. For injections and infusions, the values are higher, as expected, but it is noticeable that especially German participants in the survey place great value on a human nurse here (80% and 73% respectively).

Table 8. Preference between human and Nursing Bot

Country	Gender	Daily hygiene	Support with meals	Body creaming	Prep Medical Plan	Give injection	Give infusion
Romania	male	40%	44%	48%	52%	60%	52%
	female	40%	47%	33%	50%	60%	57%
	total	40%	45%	40%	51%	60%	55%
Germany	male	59%	56%	60%	46%	68%	66%
	female	64%	53%	53%	44%	80%	73%
	total	61%	55%	58%	46%	72%	68%

CONCLUSIONS

The results of our survey initially confirmed our expectation that Romanian participants could be more positive about the use of Cobots than German participants.

Romanian participants seem to be more open towards the new technology.

When analysing concrete services, these differences were no longer so serious. It is particularly noticeable that German participants have the greatest difficulties with body-related services provided by Nursing Bots. It also seems that German participants generally have more confidence in classic computer processes, but are unsure about robot-like processes.

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